

SECTION OF BIOLOGY AND ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES

INFLUENCE OF DIFFERENT GROWING CONDITIONS ON THE YIELD OF SPRING BARLEY IN THE SOUTHERN FOREST-STEPPE OF WESTERN SIBERIA

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Abstract

The influence of various conditions of mineral nutrition on the productivity of spring barley variety Omsky 99 in the southern forest-steppe of Western Siberia is shown. Optimization of the provision of plants with nitrogen and phosphorus ensured an increase in yield from 1.72 to 3.81 t/ha or by 122%. The closest correlation of yield in the experimental variants was with the amount of heat and moisture received in June ($r = 0.97-0.99$), that is, in more than 90% of cases, the yield of barley was determined by the weather conditions of this month ($R^2 = 0.93-0.97$).

Keywords: spring barley, productivity, soil, agroecosystem.

Cereals, as the world's main crops, play a fundamental role in ensuring food security. Among them, barley ranks fourth in terms of the amount of food and drink produced for humans, as well as animal feed [1, 2]. Barley is traditionally one of the leading grain forage crops in Western Siberia. Relatively high yield, precocity, lower demands on growing conditions determine the demand for this crop in the agricultural production of the region [3, 4]. Barley grain is an indispensable raw material for brewing, it is used in the flour-grinding and confectionery industries, cereals are produced from it, but its main purpose is feed [5]. In the diet of animals and birds, barley grain is the main ingredient, which is of paramount importance for saturating the feed with vegetable protein [6].

In a changing climate, high-yielding varieties with improved food and fodder qualities and a minimal response to adverse biotic and abiotic environmental factors are being created [7, 8]. The development of agricultural technology elements for modern intensive barley varieties used in agricultural production will

increase the realization of their very high productivity potential.

The research was carried out in 2018-2019 in long-term experiments with the use of mineral fertilizers in the crop rotation of the laboratory of field fodder production of the FSBSI "Omsk ASC", founded in 1978. The purpose of the research is to identify the response of spring barley variety Omsky 99 to different levels of mineral nutrition.

The experimental design included the following treatments: soil supply with mobile phosphorus (factor A), phosphorus fertilizer (factor B), and nitrogen fertilizer (factor C). Soil supply with mobile phosphorus was average, 50-100 mg/kg according to Chirikov (I); increased, 100-120 mg/kg (II) and 140-150 mg/kg (III); and high, 150-200 mg/kg (IV). We used two levels of application of phosphorus fertilizer (P0, P60) and three doses of nitrogen fertilizer (N0, N30, N60) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 – Field Experience Scheme

The experiment was carried out by applying fertilizers to backgrounds of different phosphorus levels in the soil.

The soil was meadow-chernozem medium-thick medium-humus heavy loamy. The reaction of the soil medium in the arable layer was neutral. The initial content of nitrate nitrogen is low, mobile phosphorus and potassium (according to Chirikov) in the control variant are medium and high, respectively. The smallest moisture capacity (SMC) for a layer of 0-0.6 m - 184 mm, 0-1.0 m - 297 mm. The occurrence of groundwater in autumn is on average at the level of 3 m.

Autumn tillage - non-moldboard to a depth of 15 cm, "STEPNYAK" KS-5.6. Moisture closure in spring against autumn backgrounds - BZSS-1.0. Before sowing cultivation - cultivator "STEPNYAK" KS-7.4.

The seeding rate of barley is 5.5 million units/ha. Sowing of barley was carried out in the third decade of May. The predecessor is soybean.

During the growing season, barley crops were once treated with herbicides to control the spread of weeds: Primadonna (0.5 l/ha) + Ovsugen Super (0.5 l/ha) + Granate (5 g/ha).

The spring barley variety Omsky 99 was created at the Omsk Agrarian Scientific Center. Bred by intra-specific hybridization of varieties followed by individual selection. This variety belongs to the forest-steppe ecological group, it is resistant to drought, the mid-season, vegetation period is 78-90 days. Over the years of study on an artificial infectious background, he showed a weak susceptibility to black and dusty smut, practically resistant to stone smut.

In terms of productivity, the variety belongs to the high-yielding varieties in the conditions of Western Siberia. The maximum yield was obtained in 2011 on the experimental fields of the Siberian Research Institute of Agriculture - 5.03 t/ha, the increase to the standard was +0.66 t/ha.

The dynamics of total moisture in the meadow-chernozem soil in the southern forest-steppe zone shows that the moisture content of spring barley was in the range from 70% SMC to SMC until the end of July in 2019 and 2020. In this interval, it is most accessible to plants, which provided normal conditions for the growth and development of culture (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 – Dynamics of total moisture in the soil in a meter layer

Barley grain yield responded to different levels of nitrogen-phosphorus nutrition. A significant increase in yield was ensured both by the pre-sowing application of phosphorus-containing fertilizers, and by the effect

of previously created backgrounds with different availability of phosphorus. On average, pre-sowing application of P60 increased the yield by 0.79 t/ha or 31%, with a higher increase 1.12 t/ha or 65% against the background with an average phosphorus content (Table 1).

Table 1

Yield of spring barley grain depending on the conditions of mineral nutrition, t/ha, 2019-2020

Mineral fertilizers		Backgrounds according to availability of P ₂ O ₅ (C)				Factor average	
phosphorus (A), kg a.i./ha	nitrogen (B), kg a.i./ha	0	I	II	III	A	B
P ₆₀	N ₆₀	2,67	3,17	3,72	3,81	3,30	3,03
	N ₃₀	2,98	3,37	3,74	3,42		
	N ₀	2,84	3,26	3,55	3,11		
P ₀	N ₆₀	1,88	2,68	2,99	3,36	2,51	2,77
	N ₃₀	2,05	2,32	2,50	3,00		
	N ₀	1,72	2,31	2,64	2,75		
Average, C		2,35	2,85	3,19	3,24		

LSD₀₅: A – 0,19 ; B – 0,24; C – 0,27; for private averages – 0,66

The aftereffect of backgrounds with increased and high content of mobile phosphorus in the soil contributed to an increase in the harvest of spring barley grain to 2.85-3.24 t/ha at 2.35 t/ha against a natural background in terms of phosphorus content.

Nitrogen fertilizers on barley are less effective, possibly due to sowing after leguminous crops, but a significant increase of 0.26 t/ha or 9% was ensured by the application of N60. The combination of the studied

factors increased the yield from 1.72 to 3.81 t/ha, or 122%.

It is worth noting the decisive role of weather conditions during the years of research in the formation of yields (Table 2). The closest correlation of yield in the experimental variants was with the amount of heat and moisture received in June ($r=0.97-0.99$), that is, in more than 90% of cases, the yield was determined by the weather conditions in June ($R^2=0.93-0.97$).

Table 2

Correlation between barley yield and hydrothermal conditions of the growing season

Year	Yield, t/ha		Hydrothermal coefficient						
	WF	MF	May-August	June-August	June-July	May	June	July	August
2018	1,75	2,9	1,31	1,05	0,98	3,14	1,22	0,74	1,24
2019	2,37	3,9 3	0,99	1,01	1,15	0,92	1,84	0,46	0,74
2020	1,12	1,4 7	0,6	0,66	0,54	0,41	0,88	0,2	0,88
Correlation (r)	WF		0,55	0,82	0,97	0,18	0,99	0,49	-0,27
	MF		0,62	0,87	0,99	0,27	0,97	0,56	-0,18
Determination coefficient (R²)	WF		0,3	0,67	0,94	0,03	0,97	0,24	0,07
	MF		0,39	0,75	0,98	0,07	0,93	0,31	0,03

Note: WF - without fertilizer, MF - mineral fertilizer (P60N60)

The combination of protective measures in agricultural technology and a moderate level of chemicalization (N30-60P60) makes it possible to realize the high biological potential of the main grain forage crop of Siberian crop production.

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